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- Poetry
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“AFRAID OF”

“In every beginning, there is always an ending”

Definitely, it is true right? Nothing in this world remains forever. Like some movies we have watched whether we like it or not, it would end. Even the oldest, strongest and biggest tree dies as the time goes by. Thus, we must accept that we too will have our end. And that, we should be ready all the time because no one knows when we are going to return this borrowed time.....borrowed life.

DEATH! We feel something inside every time we hear this five-letter word. Is it joy? Joy because we are going to rest forever and no longer be bothered by problems? Or is it fear? Fear because we are not ready to leave this wonderful world and most especially our loved ones. You? Which of these two feelings do you feel every time you hear the word death? JOY? Or Fear?

Well, in my case, I go for fear. I am afraid with this word and if only I could find ways just to resist it by all means. Sounds funny, right? Because we all know that we cannot say no to death when our time comes. Mr. D is like a thief who will come at night and steal our life. And take note, he has a lot of ways in doing it. A newborn child dies right after the mother gave birth. The one who peacefully sleeps at night but never wakes up in the morning. And worst thing of all, he gets it by means of accident, a serious disease or through a natural calamity.

Honestly, I am afraid to die. I am afraid not because I will no longer see this wonderful world, but because I don't want to see people crying and suffering because of me. Losing someone who is very important to us is not easy, right? It seems that the whole world is in our back when we see that special someone lying peacefully inside a coffin. The thought that we will not see them anymore leaves a deep wound in our hearts. A wound that aches forever. Even time cannot heal this kind of pain.

Those are the reasons why I am afraid to die. I don't want them to suffer for the rest of their lives. I could say that blessed are those who died because they won't feel the pain anymore but pity to those who lost them because they will always feel and bear the pain for the rest of their lives. How we wish that death does not exist, so we can stay here forever. Why on earth Mr. D exists? What are the reasons of its existence?

From the beginning, we all know that we just borrowed this life from our creator. With that being said, time will come that He will ask us to return it. Everything that is borrowed must be returned. So thus, our borrowed life! But why? Why are we afraid of doing it?

Human as we are, we are hesitant and afraid to give it back because we are blinded by the earthly things that surround us. Does God really love us? If he does, why he allows us to suffer through death? Yes! God loves us so much that he doesn't want us to suffer forever. It is through death that God saves us from all our sins. It is through it that God allows us to experience a life that never ends. It is his way of granting his promise, A LIFE THAT NEVER DIES!

Therefore, we should be ready all the time. Let us surrender our doubts and fears to God for he will carry us and also our loved ones during this

difficult time. No need to be afraid, for Death means a new beginning, a new start to a new life that never ends.

